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STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC POTENTIAL (A CASE STUDY OF NAMANGAN REGION)

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Abstract: This article presents theoretical views on the economic potential, infrastructure, and changes in the welfare of the population of Namangan region based on the analysis of statistical data. It also provides conclusions and recommendations through studying and analyzing the problems emerging in the region's economy.

Key words: economic growth, volume of investments, per capita income, GDP, industrial enterprises, agriculture, export volume.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada statistik ma'lumotlar tahlili asosida Namangan viloyatining iqtisodiy salohiyati, infratuzilmasi hamda aholi farovonligining qay darajada o'zgarayotgani yuzasidan nazariy fikrlar bayon etilgan. Shuningdek, viloyat iqtisodiyotida yuzaga kelayotgan muammolarni o'rganish va tahlil qilish orqali asoslangan xulosa hamda takliflar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy o'sish, investitsiyalar hajmi, aholi jon boshiga to'g'ri keladigan daromad, YIM, sanoat korxonlari, qishloq xo'jaligi, eksport hajmi.

Аннотация: В данной статье, на основе анализа статистических данных, представлены теоретические взгляды на экономический потенциал, инфраструктуру и изменения уровня благосостояния населения Наманганской области. Также даны выводы и рекомендации через изучение и анализ проблем, возникающих в экономике региона.

Ключевые слова: экономический рост, объем инвестиций, доход на душу населения, ВВП, промышленные предприятия, сельское хозяйство, объем экспорта.

INTRODUCTION

The sustainable economic development of countries is primarily determined by the extent to which they effectively utilize their regional economic potential. Rational use of available natural, economic, and labor resources in the regions, the proper location of production enterprises, the establishment of modern industrial zones, and support for the activities of business entities are among the most pressing issues today. The introduction of modern equipment and technologies into production processes, as well as the adaptation of foreign experience to local conditions, contributes to increasing efficiency and enhancing labor productivity in enterprises.

These issues are also identified as priority areas within state policy aimed at ensuring regional development. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3182¹ dated August 8, 2017, "On Priority Measures to Ensure Accelerated Socio-Economic Development of Regions," defines key objectives such as the effective use of the natural, economic, and human potential of regions, rational use of production

¹ <https://lex.uz/docs/-3302438>

and land resources, expansion of export opportunities, development of modern market infrastructure, and creation of new jobs [1]. This document emphasizes the need to implement regional development based on a comprehensive approach and to fully utilize existing potential.

At the same time, assessing regional economic development solely through individual indicators—such as the volume of industrial output, the amount of investment, or the level of technological adoption—does not yield comprehensive results. Economic growth of a region is the outcome of the interaction of multiple factors over a certain period of time; therefore, a comprehensive analysis of development, involving the joint examination of internal and external factors, is required. Demographic conditions, the structure of labor resources, the investment climate, diversification of production sectors, and the development of the services sector constitute integral components of regional economic potential.

From this perspective, studying the economic potential of Namangan region makes it possible to identify existing opportunities, assess the level of development across sectors, clarify the factors influencing economic processes, and develop proposals to address existing challenges. The region's demographic growth rates, expansion of production sectors, development of small business and entrepreneurship, as well as changes in export–import activities, necessitate an in-depth analysis of regional economic potential.

This study is aimed at analyzing the socio-economic development indicators of Namangan region on the basis of statistical data and at providing a scientific assessment of the region's existing potential and future development prospects.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

German economist Alfred Weber, in his work “Theory of the Location of Industries,” explains the location of industrial enterprises—namely, the reduction or increase of enterprise costs, transport costs, proximity to raw material sources, and the influence of labor—through a scientific model [2].

Economist August Lösch, in “The Economics of Location,” substantiates the need for economic units—such as manufacturing enterprises, sellers, or supplying entities—to identify the most optimal location centers for their activities, while also taking into account the territorial distribution of consumers. In addition, A. Lösch provides a comprehensive interpretation of the concept of agglomeration, explaining the concentration of economic activities within a single territory through the interactions, cooperation, and interdependence of enterprises, industries, and the population [3].

Moreover, numerous Uzbek economists—A. Ortiqov [4], D. Jo'rayev, Sh. Hamroyev, J. Abdurahmonov, and R. Qodirov—have, in their studies, conducted in-depth analyses of regional development, resource utilization, population distribution, urban systems, regional development strategies, assessment of socio-economic development and potential of regions, economic development strategies, regional modernization, evaluation of the effectiveness of industrial zones, economic development of rural areas, and the spatial distribution of productive forces. Based on these analyses, they have proposed scientific solutions aimed at addressing and improving existing problems in the national economy.

The methodology of this study is aimed at assessing the economic potential of Namangan region based on a comprehensive and systemic approach, grounded in the integration of theoretical concepts, statistical data, and analytical methods. The object of the research is the socio-economic development processes of Namangan region, while the subject of the research comprises the factors shaping the region's economic potential—namely, gross regional product, industrial and agricultural output, investment volume, number of enterprises, export–import indicators, employment, and demographic dynamics. The main objective of the study is to assess the current state of Namangan region's economic potential on the basis of statistical indicators, identify intersectoral changes, and substantiate development opportunities. To achieve this objective, tasks such as systematizing economic indicators, analyzing changes over time, identifying interrelationships among factors, and assessing internal and external factors influencing economic processes were carried out.

The data base of the study consists of materials from the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Namangan Regional Department of Statistics, regional economic programs, and official regulatory and legal documents. Statistical data for the period 2019–2024 were selected, as this timeframe is significant for relatively fully reflecting the effects of the pandemic, economic recovery, and changes in investment activity. A set of economic and statistical methods was applied in the analysis: horizontal analysis was used to determine annual growth rates of indicators, vertical analysis to assess the sectoral structure of gross regional product, comparative analysis to compare indicators with each other, and trend analysis to identify dynamic patterns. Graphs and diagrams were employed to visually analyze indicators such as demographic processes, investment volumes, and export–import dynamics.

In addition, the study relies on A. Weber's model of industrial location, A. Lösch's theory of regional economic development and agglomeration, as well as the scientific works of domestic economists on regional

development as its theoretical foundation. This approach made it possible to theoretically substantiate factors such as territorial location, resource utilization, spatial distribution of production, and infrastructure development that influence the formation of Namangan region's economy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

During the research process, the factors influencing economic growth were assessed in terms of their interrelationships: the growth of gross regional product was analyzed in connection with investment volumes, production activity, and the number of enterprises, while employment levels were examined in relation to industrialization and agricultural efficiency. In addition, factors such as the export–import balance, technological modernization, demographic pressure, and the condition of the labor market were studied as integral components of economic processes.

The study identified several limitations, including insufficient statistical data for certain years, the incomplete reflection of real economic conditions during the pandemic period, and the limited availability of detailed open data for some sectors. At the same time, these limitations were taken into account in the interpretation of the research results, and, in order to ensure the reliability of the analysis, the most accurate possible statistical approach was applied within the scope of available official sources.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Assessing the economic potential of regions requires the identification and elimination of existing problems, as well as the implementation of measures aimed at strengthening regions economically. In the process of economic assessment, it is necessary to systematically analyze changes in various internal and external factors. Therefore, regional economic development, improvement of living standards, attraction and effective organization of domestic and foreign investments, and expansion of production volumes through the introduction of new equipment and technologies are of critical importance. At the same time, the possibility of increasing regional economic development solely through the isolated influence of individual factors is limited; ensuring regional economic growth requires a comprehensive examination of all influencing factors.

Namangan region is geographically located in the northwestern part of the Fergana Valley. The total area of the region is 30.3 thousand km². According to statistical data, as of January 1, 2025, the population of the region amounted to 3,131.7 thousand people (Table 1) [5].

Table 1. Main macroeconomic indicators of Namangan region by years²

Indicators	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Gross Regional Product (GRP), bln soums	29,384.4	34,169.1	41,993.6	50,668.2	61,074.9	71,869.1
GRP per capita, soums	10,673,980.1	12,156,361.2	14,644,673.0	17,286,411.2	20,375,279.4	23,439,907.4
Industrial output, bln soums	8,818.1	11,011.9	14,695.1	18,120.5	21,906.8	31,696.2
Agricultural output, bln soums	15,509.0	17,913.1	21,596.0	25,157.7	30,015.6	32,497.2
Unemployment rate, %	9.1	10.6	9.7	8.9	7.0	–
Average monthly wage, soums	1,778,602.4	2,057,542.1	2,289,175.7	2,769,228.8	4,067,840.63	3,755,158.78
Number of enterprises	22,353	26,568	31,815	34,600	38,374	40,820

In 2019, the gross regional product of Namangan region amounted to 29,384.4 billion soums. The COVID-19 period caused a decline in gross domestic product and led to economic disruption not only in Namangan region but also across countries worldwide. As a result, the volume of GRP in the region decreased during this period. However, following the COVID-19 pandemic, economic recovery was observed in the regional economy, and the gross regional product began to grow gradually. By 2024, the GRP of Namangan region reached 71,869.1

² Source: Author's compilation based on data from the Namangan Regional Department of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

billion soums, which represents an increase of nearly 2.5 times compared to 2019. This growth is primarily attributed to the development of small business and the increase in investments in fixed capital aimed at regional development.

Improving the welfare of the population residing in the region, creating new jobs, and increasing real incomes are also considered important socio-economic objectives (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Population Growth Dynamics in Namangan Region³

As can be seen from the above graph, the population of Namangan region has been growing at a rapid pace. In 2019, the population of the region amounted to 2,752.9 thousand people, while by 2024 this figure had reached 3,066.1 thousand, representing an increase of 11.3% compared to 2019. Population growth in the region leads to the formation of a large labor market. Under such conditions, it is considered necessary for regional authorities to implement the following key tasks:

- improving production capacities in the region;
- establishing industrial enterprises through investments;
- creating new jobs;
- increasing export volumes;
- identifying ways to raise household incomes;
- enhancing overall living standards of the population.

As noted above, population growth also results in an increase in the volume of labor resources. The structure of labor resources includes men and women of working age (respectively 16–60 and 16–55 years), individuals older than working age who are employed, as well as individuals younger than working age who are employed (from the age of 14) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Number of Labor Resources in Namangan Region⁴

³ Source: Author's compilation based on data from the Namangan Regional Department of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

⁴ Source: Author's compilation based on data from the Namangan Regional Department of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

In 2019, the number of labor resources amounted to 1,573.9 thousand people, while by 2024 this figure had increased by 3.7% compared to 2019, reaching 1,632.4 thousand people.

In order to ensure the effective employment of a large labor force, increase incomes, and improve living standards, it is necessary to expand the number of industrial enterprises operating on the basis of innovative technologies in the region and to create new jobs. In addition, measures should be taken to expand educational coverage and introduce dual education systems to enhance the knowledge, skills, and experience of the workforce. In today's competitive market economy, education based solely on theoretical training (secondary specialized and higher education) is becoming an increasingly ineffective approach. Within the framework of the dual education system, the integration of theoretical knowledge with practical training enables the workforce to acquire skills and experience more quickly and efficiently, thereby contributing to increased economic efficiency (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Export and Import Volumes in Namangan Region during 2019–2024⁵

The issue of increasing the region's export potential remains one of the most pressing challenges. At the same time, it should be noted that the region possesses substantial agricultural land resources, significant production capacity, and a broad range of opportunities created for enterprises.

In Namangan region, the development of the service and trade sectors makes it possible to increase revenues to the regional budget, as these sectors allow relatively high returns to be generated with comparatively lower capital investment.

In addition, the volume of service imports amounted to 2.8 thousand US dollars, or 0.01% of total imports, showing no significant change compared to the corresponding period of 2019 [6]. The main components of service imports were tourism, transport, and construction services.

Under the conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic, the introduction of quarantine measures in the regions led to a sharp decline in production levels, which in turn resulted in a reduction in regional export volumes. During this period, the growth in import volumes was driven by purchases of machinery and equipment for the healthcare system and other sectors, which accounted for 50.9%, while the purchase of chemical products and related goods accounted for 18.6%.

In 2019, export volumes amounted to 356 million US dollars, while imports totaled 630.5 million US dollars. Overall, during the period 2019–2024, both export and import volumes demonstrated a simultaneous upward trend; however, the share of imports consistently exceeded that of exports. By 2024, exports had increased by nearly 60% compared to 2019, reaching 595.6 million US dollars, while imports had grown by 84.5%.

During 2019–2020, the tightening of quarantine measures and the temporary suspension of production activities led to an increase in unemployment. In this period, the unemployment rate in the region amounted

⁵ Source: Author's compilation based on data from the Namangan Regional Department of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

to 9.1% and 10.6%, respectively. Following the lifting of quarantine restrictions, employment opportunities for the economically active population expanded, making it possible to gradually reduce the unemployment rate in subsequent years (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Volume of Investments in Fixed Capital (billion soums)⁶

An increase in the volume of investments in fixed capital signifies the expansion of production capacities, intensified technical modernization, and the growth of enterprise assets within the economy. During 2019–2022, the volume of investments in fixed capital remained relatively stable. In 2019, investments in fixed capital amounted to 12,084.9 billion soums, while by 2024 this indicator had increased by nearly 4.5 times, reaching 54,231.4 billion soums. The growth in fixed capital investments contributes to the establishment of new industrial enterprises in the region or the expansion of asset volumes at existing enterprises. As a result, opportunities emerge to alleviate the unemployment problem in the region.

In 2019, 22,353 enterprises were operating in the region, whereas by 2024 this number had risen to 40,820 enterprises. Over six years, the number of enterprises nearly doubled. The region also has high potential in agricultural production. In 2019, the total value of agricultural output amounted to 15,509.0 billion soums, and this indicator increased steadily over the years. By 2024, it had nearly doubled, reaching 32,497.2 billion soums.

Over time, the increase in the number of production enterprises, along with the development of the region's leading sectors—agriculture and industry—and the resolution of existing challenges within these sectors, has enabled the creation of new jobs and an increase in wages. In 2019, the average wage amounted to 1,778,602.4 soums, while by 2024 this figure had increased by 2.1 times, reaching 3,755,158.78 soums.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In assessing the economic potential of a region, the development of the industrial, agricultural, service, and trade sectors is of particular importance. Enhancing efficiency in these sectors is achieved through the introduction of modern equipment and technologies into production processes, modernization of existing enterprises, rational use of resources, and the broad application of innovative approaches. Technological upgrades within these sectors increase economic efficiency and contribute to the region's overall economic growth.

The study results demonstrate that attracting investments and directing them toward fixed capital is a crucial factor in ensuring sustainable regional economic development. Increased investments in fixed capital enable the expansion of production capacities, the establishment of new enterprises, the growth of assets at existing enterprises, and technical and technological modernization. This process directly contributes to the growth of the region's gross domestic product.

The growing number of industrial enterprises leads to greater diversification of the regional economy, increased demand in the labor market, and a reduction in unemployment. Ensuring employment in line with professional qualifications, rising wages, and increasing real incomes not only strengthens economic stability but also improves the overall standard of living of the population.

⁶ Source: Author's compilation based on data from the Namangan Regional Department of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Overall, sectoral economic growth, intensified investment activity, increased export potential, a rising number of enterprises, and positive changes in household incomes in Namangan region indicate a steady increase in the region's economic potential. To sustain this process in the future, it is necessary to modernize key sectors, widely introduce innovative technologies, diversify exports, and develop comprehensive measures aimed at further increasing employment.

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